

D6.13 Report of the third CPD module in One Health

Continuing Professional Development Module 2022 – Rapid Diagnostics and Harmonisation of Diagnostic Tests

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partners: 13-SSI, 12-DTU

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	69 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	Report of the fourth CPD module in One Health		
WP and task	WP6, Task 6.5		
Lead Organising Institute	SSI		
Lead Event Organiser	SSI		
Local Organising Committee	13-SSI, 12-DTU		
Collaborating Organising Institutes	12-DTU		
Collaborating Organisers	Support from OHEJP Communications Team		
Due month of the deliverable	60		
Actual submission month	62		
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

	<p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>WHO-EURO <input type="checkbox"/> WOH <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s):</u></p>
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Introduction

The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) Continuing Professional Development (CPD) module 2022 was held on 2nd – 4th November in Copenhagen, Denmark and was hosted by Statens Serum Institut (OHEJP partner 13-SSISSI¹) and the Technical University of Denmark, National Food Institute (OHEJP partner 13-DTU²). The theme of the module was rapid diagnostics and the harmonisation of diagnostics tests with a special focus on One Health surveillance (OHS).

The overall concept for this CPD module was to bring microbiologists and epidemiologists together in the laboratory and at the desk to emphasise the importance of harmonised diagnostics in an outbreak setting. The module was delivered in a hybrid format; those participating in person worked together in and out of the laboratory to perform a case study of an *E. coli* outbreak and online participants worked independently on a case study regarding an outbreak of cryptosporidiosis among veterinary students. The module began with introductory lectures from the invited keynote speaker as well as several experts from the hosting OHEJP partner institutes and ended with a common restitution session.

A key highlight of the CPD module was the hands-on microbiological analyses that the in person participants conducted in the laboratory as a part of the *E. coli* case study. All of the participants, including those with a microbiology background, were curious and engaged during the laboratory work and reported learning something new during these exercises. Participants were able to collaborate and work through various exercises and analyses together, making the lab work exciting and interactive. Another key success was the writing and design of both case studies utilised in the module, which were created in line with the teaching objectives of this CPD. The *E. coli* case study microbiology component was written by Susanne Jespersen, Sarah Marvig Johansson and Nadia Boisen and the epidemiology component was written by Luise Müller and Emily Dibba White. The cryptosporidiosis case study was written by Guido Benedetti and utilised knowledge gathered by OHEJP JIPs MATRIX and OH-Harmony-CAP as well as JRP PARADISE.

Theme and Overview

The 2022 OHEJP CPD module had the theme of rapid diagnostics and the harmonisation of diagnostics tests in a One Health context. SSI and DTU Food hosted this hybrid CPD module both in person in Copenhagen, Denmark as well as online, with participants across multiple continents participating. This training module drew from the experiences and knowledge of three OHEJP JIPs: OH-Harmony-CAP, CARE, and MATRIX to highlight the importance of standardized and harmonized laboratory methods in an outbreak scenario from both the microbiological and epidemiological perspectives. *E. coli* and *Cryptosporidium* were the two pathogens utilised in this module to demonstrate the significance to harmonized diagnostic methods, with a particular focus on outbreak investigation. A One Health approach was adopted in the module and case studies to highlight the importance of taking a multi-sectoral and cross-disciplinary approach when investigating outbreaks.

¹ SSI's website: "<https://en.ssi.dk/>

² DTU Food's website : <https://www.food.dtu.dk/english>

Aims and Objectives

The main objective of this module was to explore the role of diagnostics and related challenges from both the microbiological and epidemiological perspectives during an outbreak investigation. The event therefore aimed to:

- Actively engage epidemiologists and microbiologists in the different roles that each group plays during an outbreak scenario.
- Improve participants understanding of the perspectives of each professional group when dealing with an outbreak, focusing on the effects of applying rapid and/or harmonized diagnostic tests.

Hybrid Format

The CPD module was conducted in a hybrid format, with an in-person and an online capacity of 24 and 100 participants, respectively. The online audience was invited via Microsoft Teams to join the following sessions:

- Session A - Welcome and introduction, keynote speaker, and additional lectures on various related topics by experts from both SSI and DTU Food relevant for the two case studies.
- Session F - Restitution and summation of CPD experience from microbiological and epidemiological perspectives from both case studies, module evaluation, and closing remarks.

It was decided to host the CPD event in hybrid format in late 2021, when the authors of the application applied to host the module to ensure optimal timing in terms of the outcomes from the related OHEJP projects. A hybrid format was chosen to ensure the broadest reach of the CPD module possible, while still allowing those who are able to attend in person the opportunity for a hands-on experience, including time in the laboratory. The hybrid format allowed for flexibility in the agenda and layout of the module, giving participants the option of joining in a way that aligned with their schedules and available resources and was therefore, a more inclusive format for the module.

Programme Structure

Before CPD module start

No reading/preparatory materials were provided to participants before the module. Participants were instructed to have laptops with them and that all other materials would be provided to them throughout the module. No further preparation was required.

Overall agenda

The CPD module was broken down into six sessions over three days. In Figure 1 below, the orange sessions represent the two hybrid sessions, and the four blue sessions represent the two case studies that were not conducted in a hybrid format.

	Morning Session 9:00 – 12:00	Afternoon Session 13:00 – 15:30
Wednesday	Session A	Session B
Thursday	Session C	Session D
Friday	Session E	Session F

Figure 1 - Six CPD sessions over three days.

Session A was an introductory session for in person and online participants and was conducted in a hybrid format using Microsoft Teams. All participants were welcomed to DTU by Rene Hendriksen, professor and JIP-CARE project lead, and Caroline Eves, CPD coordinator and JIP-MATRIX project member. Caroline then gave a brief presentation introducing participants to the host institutes of the CPD module (SSI and DTU Food), OHEJP, JIPs CARE, OH-Harmony-Cap, and MATRIX, the learning objectives, and the overall layout of the module session.

The keynote address was given by Dr. Peter Gerner-Smidt of the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Division of Foodborne, Waterborne, and Environmental Diseases, Atlanta, Georgia, USA. Peter discussed the importance of harmonisation of laboratory methods across sectors and presented the well-developed, American model for harmonisation of methods and data sharing in a One Health context. He presented practical examples of zoonotic outbreaks from the United States, which demonstrated how harmonized methods play a key role in outbreak investigations.

After the keynote address, several lectures were given to introduce participants to relevant concepts they would need to know before embarking on their respective case studies. Firstly, Nadia Boisen, OH-Harmony-Cap project lead and Senior Scientist at SSI, presented about harmonization of diagnostic methods from the European perspective, strengths and weakness of the current system, and the work that both CARE and OH-Harmony-Cap have been doing to harmonize methods and provide reference materials. Flemming Scheutz, *E. coli* expert and scientist at SSI, then introduced participants to various pathogenic *E. coli* strains, why they are so difficult to work with in the laboratory, and what can be done to combat these challenges. Jette Sejer Kjeldgaard, Senior Scientific Officer at DTU Food and member of the Research Group for Global Capacity Building, presented about whole genome sequencing, genomic epidemiology, and CGE bioinformatic tools, providing the basics regarding sequencing and cluster identification and analysis. Finally, Emily Dibba White, member state EPIET fellow and epidemiologist in the Outbreak Investigation Team at SSI, presented the 10 steps of outbreak investigation from the epidemiological perspective, including how to calculate odds ratio and create and epidemic curve.

At the conclusion of the session, all participants were sent PDF versions of the lecture presentations to refer back to as they embarked on their respective case studies. The online participants were sent the case study on an outbreak of cryptosporidiosis among veterinary students in Denmark. This case study was intended to be a self-guided exercise for online participants to undergo during the non-hybrid sessions of the module. Online participants were dismissed and invited to rejoin the CPD module online for an optional meeting on Thursday from 13:00-14:30 for an open discussion on the cryptosporidiosis case study with Guido Benedetti, which was added to the schedule after the final program had been published. Online participants were also encouraged to join for the final hybrid Session F on Friday afternoon at 13:00.

Session B introduced the *E. coli* case study to the in person participants, setting the scene for the outbreak. Participants were then divided into three groups, each with a mix of microbiologists and epidemiologists from different institutes and countries. Everyone transitioned into the laboratory to start the microbiological analyses portion of the case study. Participants received a packet of reference materials for the laboratory exercises, explaining the analysis procedures, how to interpret results, and what those results revealed about the potential cause of the outbreak. Participants were encouraged to ask questions and use the session facilitators as resources throughout their time in the laboratory. Facilitators in the laboratory included Susanne Jespersen (SSI), Sarah Marvig Johansson (DTU Food), Nadia Boisen (SSI), and Rene Hendriksen (DTU Food).

Participants analysed bacterial morphology by testing for lactose susceptibility on agar plates. Slide agglutination of the live cultures was also performed using OK O antisera to test for virulent strains in the VTEC and EPEC pathogenic groups. H serotyping was conducted using semi-solid agar to test for bacteria motility. Test tube agglutination was also tested for to further determine motility of the bacteria.

Session C began with additional O serotyping using O antisera panel as well as H serotyping. Participants then prepared and carried out a PCR analysis.

Sessions B and C provided time for online participants to work on the *Cryptosporidium* case study independently with the option to reach out to Guido Benedetti via email should they have a question/need clarification.

Session D started with the final laboratory component of the *E. coli* case study. Participants used the solution prepared in the previous session to load and run a PCR gel. The results of this test were interpreted to determine the pathotypes based on the virulence genes present in the *E. coli* samples participants had been working with throughout the entire cases study.

This session also introduced the epidemiological component of the case study, shifting participants out of the laboratory and over to the desktop. Participants were re-divided into new groups of 3-4 people who were not in a laboratory group together, keeping a mix of epidemiologists and microbiologists in each group. Each group was led through the epidemiology portion of the case study by a facilitator familiar with the outbreak and case study. These facilitators included SSI epidemiologists Luise Müller, Emily Dibba White, and Guido Benedetti/Caroline Eves.

The epidemiology portion of the case study was broken down into three sections. The first section, entitled “Case definition and descriptive epidemiology”, acted as a continuation of the outbreak investigation from the laboratory, where information was passed from the microbiologists in the laboratory to the epidemiologists. In this section, participants discussed the meaning of “endemic”, how to define an outbreak, what to consider when creating either a broad or specific case definition using the elements of time, place and person, and how to visualise outbreak data by making an epidemic curve.

After a short break, participants started on the next section of the epidemiology portion of the case study entitled “Patient interviews and hypothesis generation”. In this section, participants were guided through how to conduct hypothesis generating interviews, including which patients to prioritise interviewing and what questions to ask them. Then, based on sample interview results similar to those collected during the actual outbreak investigation, participants were then challenged to describe their hypotheses and how they would move forward with the investigation.

During Session D, from 13:00 – 14:30, online participants had the opportunity to join Guido Benedetti for an optional online meeting via Microsoft Teams to discuss various aspects of the *Cryptosporidium* case study and work through any issues they were having. Guido remained online for the 1.5-hour session to give participants the flexibility to come and go as their schedules allowed. This meeting was not intended to be a walk-through of the full case study, but rather to address any questions online participants may have as they independently worked through the case study.

Session E was the first session taking place at SSI, which wrapped up both the microbiological and epidemiological components of the *E. coli* case study.

The session opened with the third and final section of the epidemiology portion of the *E. coli* case study, where participants worked on choosing and designing an analytical study to perform and then analysing the results of that study, including calculating odds ratios. Once the cause of the outbreak was determined, participants discussed strategies for the communication of the results of the investigation with stakeholders and the general public.

After a short break, Nadia Boisen concluded the microbiological component of the case study by summarising the various *E. coli* pathotypes and the different virulence factors associated with each one. She then revisited the CGE tools Jette Sejer Kjeldgaard discussed in Session A and went through, step by step, how participants can upload the *E. coli* sequences of the two serotypes (O96 and O136) discovered in the laboratory using SerotypeFinder-2.0 and how to use VirulenceFinder-2.0 to understand the virulence genes associated with these strains.

This session concluded with a one-hour, interactive presentation by Guido Benedetti on the case study about an outbreak of cryptosporidiosis among veterinary students. Due to the lack of time, in person participants were introduced to the outbreak and presented with the initial challenges faced by the investigation team. This presentation was formatted similarly to a large focus group, where in person participants played an active role in problem solving and progressing through the introduction of the case study and overall outbreak. Among the participants were several veterinarians, who were keen to share their experiences regarding veterinary school and the risks, zoonotic and otherwise, they faced during their respective

academic programs. This presentation intended to act as a teaser, catching the interest of in person participants and encouraging them to independently complete the case study on their own time after the CPD module. This lecture was included by the CPD planning team to ensure that the in person participants had a brief introduction to *Cryptosporidium* and the work the online participants had been executing over the past several days, in order to make the restitution more dynamic and relevant for both participant groups.

Session F was the second of two hybrid sessions to the CPD module, where the online participants joined via Microsoft Teams. A joint restitution was held by Luise Müller, reviewing each of the case studies, their respective challenges regarding harmonisation of laboratory methods, and elements the two outbreaks had in common. The importance of harmonisation in the One Health arena, particularly when it comes to laboratory methodologies, was emphasized here – regardless of the pathogen at hand, harmonisation is key to making the results comparable between contexts and even countries. At the end of this restitution, the three JIP project leaders and members of the CPD planning team were invited to share what harmonization in One Health meant to them. This portion of the activity took the shape of an informal round table discussion, where elements from each of the JIPs (CARE, OH-Harmony-Cap, and MATRIX) were highlighted and discussed in relationship to one another, also in conjunction with the experiences from the in person and online audiences.

After the activity and a short break, online and in person participants were given a link to two separate CPD module evaluations (specifics regarding these evaluations are described below). Participants were then given approximately 25 minutes to complete their respective evaluations. The evaluation was built into the agenda of the CPD module to encourage participants to provide feedback while the module was still fresh in their minds. Additionally, it was assumed that less feedback could be expected had the evaluation been distributed after the CPD module was complete. Therefore, integrating it into the agenda ensured that the CPD planning team received as much feedback as possible.

The final component of the last session of the CPD module was a summary of lessons learned, given by Rene Hendriksen, Nadia Boisen, and Caroline Eves. Key takeaways from each of the three JIPs were reiterated, emphasising the importance of harmonized laboratory methods within One Health and the impact that harmonisation has across the full surveillance pipeline, from the microbiological to the epidemiological components of outbreak investigation.

This concluded the CPD module.

Additional networking continued among in person participants after the end of Session F, with many exchanging professional and personal contact information as well as plans to coordinate during upcoming conferences, etc. Before leaving, several in person participants requested printed copies of the *Cryptosporidium* case study so that they could work on it during their journey home.

Experts, Speakers, and the CPD module planning team

Biographies and photos of the experts and speakers can be found on the OHEJP CPD 2022 website.

Keynote speaker: Dr. Peter Gerner-Smidt travelled to Denmark to speak at this CPD module from Atlanta, Georgia, USA, where he is employed at the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Division of Foodborne, Waterborne, and Environmental Diseases. His expertise working with foodborne outbreaks in a setting with comprehensive and cohesive harmonization of laboratory methods was extremely valuable for this CPD module, and further demonstrated the importance of harmonization and its many benefits from the American perspective.

Dr. Nadia Boisen is a senior scientist at the International Centre for Reference and Research on *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella*, Statens Serum Institut, Denmark and visiting Associate Professor, University of Virginia School of Medicine, USA. She has over 15 years of experience with pathogenic *E. coli*, international collaborations through research projects, and high-impact publications on the subject and is one of the leading experts on Enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EAEC) in particular Shiga toxin producing EAEC (STEC-EAEC). She is also the project leader of the OHEJP JIP OH-Harmony-CAP, which focuses on the harmonization of laboratory protocols for the detection of foodborne pathogens and AMR. Her expertise regarding *E. coli* as well as her involvement in the original outbreak investigation that inspired the *E. coli* case study made her a key player in the development of this CPD module. She was also a core member of the CPD planning team. In her presentations, Nadia introduced OH-Harmony-CAP to participants, and quickly dove into the paramount importance of harmonization of laboratory methods in the context of an outbreak investigation.

Dr. Rene Hendriksen is a professor at the Technical University of Denmark, National Food Institute, and lead the Research Group of Global Capacity Building. He acts as director of the World Health Organization (WHO) Collaborating Centre, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) Reference Center, and European Union Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) and Genomics, respectively. In addition, Rene is the project leader for the OHEJP JIP CARE, which focuses on providing reference materials and developing proficiency testing for laboratories from a One Health perspective. Rene was also a core member of the CPD planning team. His many years of experience working with One Health, experience conducting over 25 international training courses, in addition to his expertise in global epidemiology and microbiology brought enormous value to the CPD module.

Dr. Guido Benedetti is a dentist with many years of experience working with humanitarian organizations and international agencies. Guido is an epidemiologist in the Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology & Prevention at SSI. He has immense experience participating in and conducting case studies and was a part of the original *Cryptosporidium* outbreak investigation team. He also possesses expertise in epidemiological analyses and was crucial to the success of both case studies. Guido is also the project leader of the JIP MATRIX project and part of the core planning team of this CPD module.

Luise Müller is an epidemiologist with expertise in infectious disease field epidemiology. Her key area of interest and main role in her position at SSI is outbreak investigation of foodborne

outbreaks and surveillance of zoonoses. As head of the disease outbreak unit, she has a coordinating role in health preparedness and response activities. She is an experienced epidemiologist and led the outbreak unit through the original *E. coli* outbreak investigation from the epidemiological side. She has also been involved in many case studies and was therefore of great value to the writing and facilitating of the *E. coli* case study.

Emily Dibba White is an epidemiologist with focus on food- and waterborne outbreaks and surveillance of zoonoses at SSI. She is currently enrolled in the European Programme for Intervention Epidemiology Training (EPIET) by European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). She played a crucial role in the original *E. coli* outbreak investigation from the epidemiological side and was paramount in the writing and facilitating the case study. She has expertise in outbreak investigation and epidemiology, in addition to her experience with case studies from her EPIET fellowship, making her an essential part of the CPD team.

Susanne Jespersen is a laboratory technician with over 45 years of experience working with *E. coli* at SSI as a part of the Department of Bacteria, Parasites and Fungi. In that time, she has seen the development of methods and approaches from the basic microbiology to whole genome sequencing. Her immense expertise regarding *E. coli* and related laboratory methods highlighted the importance of harmonization of diagnostic methods. Susanne played a major role in the development and execution of the microbiology component of the *E. coli* case study.

Sarah Marvig Johansson is a laboratory technician for the research group for Global Capacity Building at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU). She has worked with both routine diagnostics and research of bacteria, fungi and parasites and has experience with phenotypic susceptibility testing. She has been involved in the planning of numerous international training courses and has expertise in phenotypic testing and teaching those methods. She was an essential member of the CPD planning team and played a major role in the development and execution of the microbiology component of the *E. coli* case study.

Dr. Flemming Scheutz is head of the International Centre for Reference and Research on *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella* at the Department of Bacteria, Parasites and Fungi at SSI. His area of expertise is *E. coli*, including pathogenic strains, which he presented to CPD participants.

Dr. Jette Sejer Kjeldgaard is a Senior Scientific Officer at DTU Food and is a part of the research group for Global Capacity Building. She presented about whole genome sequencing and CGE bioinformatics tools to participants.

Dr. Pikka Jokelainen is the leader of Secretariat for Infectious Disease Preparedness at SSI and had a supportive role in the core planning team of this CPD module. She is a Project Management Team member of OHEJP and participant in JIP OH-Harmony-CAP and JRP PARADISE. She is one of the co-authors of the article that the *Cryptosporidium* case study was based on.

Caroline Eves was the coordinator of this CPD module and is an epidemiologist in the Section for Food and Waterborne Zoonoses in the Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology and Prevention at SSI. She is also a JIP MATRIX consortium member and is responsible for the Danish contribution to the project. Additionally, she has international experience working in

infectious disease surveillance and emergency response. She led the CPD planning team and was in charge of organizing and running the CPD 2022 module as well as authoring this report.

Logistical arrangements

Organisational and planning process

The core CPD planning team consisted of Rene Hendriksen from DTU Food and Caroline Eves, Guido Benedetti, Nadia Boisen, and Pikka Jokelainen from SSI.

The CPD planning team held bi-weekly working group meetings starting in May 2022 through to the end of the summer. These meetings included the core CPD planning team, where members brainstormed various ideas for the focus and layout of the module. By the start of the summer, the CPD planning team had agreed to use the two case studies within the module, one on *E. coli* and one on *Cryptosporidium*. It was also agreed upon that the module would be open to both microbiologists and epidemiologists, inviting epidemiologists into the laboratory and microbiologists to join the epidemiology work. This cross-pollination and “role-reversal” concept would give each group the opportunity to experience the work and challenges of the other, especially regarding One Health and harmonization of methods (or lack thereof) during an outbreak investigation.

Luise Müller and Emily Dibba White were invited to join the planning team as well as write and lead the epidemiology portion of the *E. coli* case study and prepare an introductory and restitution presentation during the hybrid sessions. They were also facilitators for the epidemiology portion of the case study. Susanne Jespersen and Sarah Marvig Johansson were invited to design and lead the microbiology component of the *E. coli* case study as well as laboratory exercises. Susanne Jespersen, Sarah Marvig Johansson, Nadia Boisen, and Rene Hendriksen were facilitators for the microbiology component of the case study. Starting at the beginning of September through the actual event, CPD planning meetings were held on a weekly basis.

Guido Benedetti led the work to design and author the cryptosporidiosis case study. Pikka Jokelainen contributed with pathogen-specific expertise and coordination. Caroline Eves contributed to the writing, design, and copy editing of the case study.

Branded communication materials designed by the OHEJP Communications team were used for the CPD module, which helped to maintain cohesive advertising and overall theme of the event. This was particularly beneficial to participants from outside of the OHEJP consortium and provided clear and concise branding for the CPD module.

IT support, both at DTU Food and SSI, was hired by the CPD planning team to set up microphones, internet access, etc. as well as to provide additional support during the two hybrid sessions. This helped to ensure smooth transitions between presentations and an overall cohesive experience for the online audience.

The hybrid format was considered important in order to increase inclusiveness of the module. However, the hybrid component of the module also brought several challenges with it. Firstly,

it was challenging to create engaging content and exercises regarding laboratory methods for online participants. The CPD planning team could accommodate in person participants in the laboratory and was excited to have practical exercises in the laboratory to emphasise the importance of harmonized methods. Knowing this, the challenge then became how to equally engage those attending online to deliver the same message. The solution to this was to create a completely separate and self-led case study that the online participants could work through while the in person participants spent time in the laboratory.

Additionally, certain technical difficulties arose, as is often unavoidable when working with virtual meetings. Despite extra IT support, issues with cameras not working properly and microphones not picking up sound from the in person audience occurred. However, these issues did not disrupt the flow of the presentations nor the energy from participants or CPD planning team. All issues were resolved quickly, and the module continued on as planned.

Participant engagement

Session A was the initial contact participants had with the CPD module, and the CPD planning team/lecturers wanted to immediately portray an atmosphere of openness and curiosity, where anyone could ask questions and add their own experiences to the discussions. During Session F, online participants were invited to turn on their cameras and “meet” the in person participants during the restitution, engaging them directly with the in person participants and facilitators.

For the in person case study, participants were encouraged to interact with each other during the various group work exercises, both in and out of the laboratory. The groups were small, which created an intimate atmosphere where participants could speak freely, ask questions, and discuss various aspects of the module with other participants and facilitators alike. Working through the case study in smaller groups ensured that everyone had the opportunity to contribute and have their voice be heard.

The online participants spent the majority of sessions working independently on the case study. However, to ensure that they were also engaged and able to interact with CPD facilitators as well as other online participants, the online audience was invited to attend a 1.5 hour open online meeting. Here, Guido Benedetti was online and available to discuss various aspects of the case study and any questions participants had in the form of an open focus group discussion.

Promotional Campaign

The One Health EJP social media platforms of Twitter and LinkedIn were used to promote the CPD module. Bespoke banners were created to advertise the event. This initially started from May 2022, with “Save the date” social media posts disseminated from May to July, and subsequently “Register now” social media posts disseminated during August and September 2022. After the registration deadline had closed, social media posts provided a countdown to the event start date and on 2nd November the post “OHEJP CPD 2022 module starts today!” was shared. Post event, a “Congratulations to the OHEJP CPD module organisers” post was disseminated on 11th November 2022. A blog post celebrating the success of this event (written by Jennifer Cantlay and reviewed/approved by Caroline Eves) was added to the OHEJP

website on 1st December, with social media to advertise the blog shared on 2nd and 20th December (the latter as a reminder about this blog post). An infographic was created to accompany these posts from photos taken during the event, that participants had given their consent to share publicly.

Information on the CPD module was also included on the OHEJP website in a Latest News post disseminated on 22nd August 2022 to promote participant registration. The CPD module 2022 webpage was frequently updated to add the flyer, agenda, speaker biographies and registration information and our social media posts referred our followers to this webpage. Articles were included in the June, September, and November 2022 Consortium (internal) newsletters to advertise the event. The December 2022 external newsletter included an article celebrating the success of the CPD module and provided a link to the blog post on the OHEJP website.

The Communications Team also shared news of this CPD module externally with the One Health Commission, as a short article included in “One Health Happenings” newsletter for October/November 2022.

Some examples of the social media banners used in the campaign are shown below:

Continuing Professional Development Module:

Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests

2-4 November, Copenhagen and online

Registration closed!

Applications and selection procedure

Application

The registration form was created by OHEJP Comminutions using Google forms as a questionnaire. The registration form included the following introductory text:

“Diagnostic tests are a key part of investigating and managing an outbreak. New diagnostic methods, including rapid diagnostics, are available and efforts have been made to harmonise diagnostic tests across laboratories and across sectors. This module will discuss the role of diagnostics and related challenges from both the microbiological and epidemiological perspectives. Outbreak case studies based on real outbreaks will actively engage both epidemiologists and microbiologists, walking participants through the different roles that each group plays during an outbreak scenario. Epidemiologists will accompany microbiologists in the laboratory to gain a better understanding of various testing procedures (e.g. PCR, serotyping, whole genome sequencing) and microbiologists will join epidemiologists in conducting epidemiological analyses typical during an outbreak investigation. This structure will allow each group to improve their understanding of the perspectives of the other when dealing with an outbreak together, focusing on the effects of applying rapid and/or harmonised diagnostic tests. The module will draw from the experiences and new knowledge from three One Health EJP Joint Integrative Projects: OH-Harmony-CAP, MATRIX and CARE.

This CPD training module is geared towards PhD students and One Health professionals in the early stages of their careers. The training will be run by Statens Serum Institut and Technical University of Denmark, National Food Institute, and will take place partly in a laboratory setting and partly as a desktop exercise. Participants will need to bring a laptop with them. No additional preparation is required.

Location: Copenhagen, Denmark

Dates: Wednesday – Friday, November 2 - 4, 2022

Please submit the form below to apply. The application deadline is Friday, September 23, 2022. If you are selected to participate, you will receive a confirmation email no later than Friday, September 30, 2022.

The agenda and other relevant information are available here: [CPD 2022 - One Health EJP](#)

Additionally, the following disclaimer regarding SSI's use of personal data was provided:

"The data submitted through this form will be disclosed to Statens Serum Institut, as they are organizing the event. Read more about how SSI processes your data below:

How we process your personal data

We will process your personal data in connection with your registration to the One Health European Joint Programme's Continuing Professional Development (CPD) module, hosted by Statens Serum Institut (SSI) and DTU Food. See below for further information regarding the processing of your personal data when registering for the CPD module at SSI.

Data controller for the processing of personal data

*Statens Serum Institut
Artillerivej 5
2300 Copenhagen S
CVR No .: 46 83 74 28
Tel: +45 3268 3268
E-mail: serum@ssi.dk*

Data Protection Officer

The Ministry of Health has a shared data protection officer (DPO), Helle Ginnerup-Nielsen, who is employed by the Department of the Ministry of Health. The DPO can be contacted at databeskyttelse@sum.dk. SSI has a local compliance division, which can be contacted at compliance@ssi.dk.

The purposes of the treatment

We process your personal information with the purpose of registering your participation in the webinar and in order to forward relevant information regarding the webinar.

The legal basis for the treatment

The processing of personal data is based on the General Data Protection Regulation, Article 6 (1), litra f.

Please be aware that Microsoft also processes personal data about you when you log on to the webinar, which will be hosted via your connection to Microsoft Teams. If you use a private license for Microsoft Teams, it is a relation between you and Microsoft. If you use a license that your employer has made available to you, it will probably be a relation between you and your employer. Read more about Microsoft's processing of personal data [here](#).

Categories of personal information

We process the following categories of personal data about you:

- Name*
- E-mail address*
- Employer*
- Country of Residence*
- Current position*

Recipients of the personal data

We do not share your personal data with others.

However, please be aware that Microsoft also processes personal data about you when you log on to the webinar, which will be hosted via Microsoft Teams. In some cases, Microsoft uses subcontractors outside the EU / EEA. Read more about Microsoft's processing of personal data [here](#).

Deletion of your personal data

After the completion of the webinar and once the evaluation form and other material has been sent, your personal data will be deleted.

You have the right to request the following:

- The right to request insight into the processing of personal data*
- The right to request limitation of treatment*
- The right to request the correction of personal data*
- The right to request data portability*
- The right to object to a treatment*
- The right to request deletion*

You should be aware that there may be a number of restrictions on your rights that follow from the Data Protection Regulation and the Danish Data Protection Act.

You have the right to complain to the Danish Data Protection Agency

To find more information, visit www.datatilsynet.dk.”

As a part of their application, applicants were asked to provide their first and last names, email address, country of residence, affiliated institute, current role, whether they consider themselves a microbiologist or epidemiologist, and whether they would prefer to participate in person or online.

Applicants

In all, 57 individuals from 30 countries spanning across four continents registered for participation in the CPD module (see Table 1). Among these, 13 registered for in person attendance and 44 for online participation. There were slightly more microbiologists than epidemiologists that applied, at 37 and 20, respectively. Figure 2 shows the reported academic and professional backgrounds of applicants, the most common being Researcher/Professor and PhD student/PostDoc with 22 and 15 applicants, respectively. All applicants were invited to participate in the CPD module.

Table 1. Reported countries of residence among OHEJP CPD module 2022 applicants

Countries
Armenia
Austria
Bangladesh
Belgium
Brazil
Cameroon
Denmark
Ethiopia
France
Germany
Greece
Iceland
India
Italy
Jordan
Latvia
Nepal
Netherlands
Nigeria
Philippines
Poland
Portugal
Turkey
Romania
Slovenia
Spain
Sweden
Switzerland
Ukraine
United Kingdom

Figure 2. Academic and professional backgrounds of OHEJP CPD module 2022 applicants

Delegates

In total, 31 individuals from 14 countries participated in the CPD module. Of these, nine were in person participants and 22 were online participants. 10 participants identified as epidemiologists and 21 as microbiologists. Table 2 shows the 14 countries participants reported as their countries of residence at the time of registration.

Table 2. Countries of residence of OHEJP CPD module 2022 participants

Countries
Denmark
Iceland
India
Italy
Netherlands
Poland
Portugal
Turkey
Romania
Slovenia
Spain
Switzerland
Ukraine
United Kingdom

Figure 3. Academic and professional backgrounds of CPD 2022 participants

Figure 3 shows the reported academic and professional backgrounds of CPD 2022 module participants, with ‘Researcher/Professor’ being the most common at 13 participants followed by ‘Other’ and ‘PhD student/PostDoc’ with 12 and six participants, respectively. This profile of participants matched the intended audience of this CPD module, namely PhD students and One Health professionals in the early stages of their careers. Many participants from a research background were fellows, research associates, and research assistants, implying that they are at the beginning of their careers. The same goes for PhD students and PostDocs, who were also in the early phases of their careers. There were also other types of students and fellows in attendance, which matched the target audience of the CPD module. Participants included professionals both in and outside of the OHEJP consortium, creating a variety in understanding of and experience working with One Health. This resulted in a more dynamic and interactive group, who were curious and able to support one another through the CPD module process.

Course Evaluation

For this CPD module, two different anonymous evaluations were created: one for the in-person participants and one for online participants. Both evaluations aimed to capture the quality of the module itself and how the different groups of participants experienced the various components of the module. Both evaluations were created using the web platform Analyzer in the form of a short questionnaire with the option to leave a comment to accompany each response. While each evaluation focused largely on the respective case studies, both participant groups were asked about the introductory lectures given in Session A as well as their overall level of satisfaction with the CPD module as a whole.

General evaluation hybrid joint CPD module - Sessions A and F

The following questions were included in the general evaluation of the hybrid components of the CPD module:

- *On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree, please respond to the following statements:*
 - *The CPD module fulfilled the learning objectives that were proposed.*
 - *The CPD module met my own professional goals.*

- *I learned something new from the series of introductory lectures in Session A.*
- *The introductory lectures were informative, interesting, and easily understandable.*
- *The various lectures prepared me for the case study.*

Please provide comments to support each of your responses.

- *On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is very poor and 5 is very positive, please respond to the following question:*
 - *How would you rate your overall experience being a part of this CPD module?*

Please provide comments to support your answer.

Evaluation for in person participants

E. coli Case Study: In person participants were given an evaluation regarding the *E. coli* case study and were asked the following questions:

- *On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is disagree and 5 is agree, please respond to the following statements:*
 - *The case study was coherent, logical and easy to complete on my own.*
 - *The content and materials of the case study provided the information needed to successfully complete the case study.*

Please provide comments to support each of your responses.

Cryptosporidium Case Study: In person participants were given a short evaluation regarding the *Cryptosporidium* case study teaser from Session F and were asked to respond to the following statements:

- *Please describe one thing that you liked about this session.*
- *Please describe one thing that you did not like about this session.*

Evaluation for online participants

Online participants were given an evaluation of the *Cryptosporidium* case study and asked the following questions/statements:

- *On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is disagree and 5 is agree, please respond to the following statements:*
 - *The case study was coherent, logical and easy to complete on my own.*
 - *The content of the case study provided the information needed to successfully complete the case study.*

Please provide comments to support each of your responses.

- *Please describe one thing that you liked about the case study.*

- Please describe one thing about the case study that you think could be improved.
- Any additional suggestions or comments regarding the case study?

Evaluation Responses

Eight in person and nine online participants responded to their respective evaluations. The evaluations reported that overall, participants from the in person and online audiences were pleased with their experience at the CPD module and felt that the learning objectives of the module were met. Participants also reported that both case studies were well written and connected to the overall theme of the module. No additional comments were provided in either evaluation.

While both evaluations provided highly positive feedback, the in person responses to the evaluation were slightly more positive than the online responses. This highlights the challenges in engaging an online audience to the same degree as an in person audience, especially considering the theme of the module, which focused on the harmonisation of laboratory methods.

Certificates of Attendance

The Certificates of Attendance were designed and created by the OHEJP Communications team and signed by Caroline Eves and Roberto La Ragione. Once completed, the certificate template was sent to Caroline Eves, who personalised and distributed the PDF version of the certificates to participants via email on November 10, the week after the CPD module.

Post-event communications

Blog Post

A blog post celebrating the success of this event (written by Jennifer Cantlay and reviewed/approved by Caroline Eves) was added to the OHEJP website on 1st December. This can be seen at: <https://onehealthjep.eu/cpd-2022/>. Additionally, social media promoting this blog post was shared on 2nd and 20th December (the latter as a reminder). An infographic was created to accompany these posts using photos taken during the event, which participants had given their consent to share publicly.

Testimonials

A testimonial from one participant was included in the blog post as follows: Charlotte Kjelsø from SSI said “For me there was an overall profit from meeting colleagues and get familiar with work within other relevant fields of one health than my own. And I wish that modules like this will be part of every country’s own strategy for implementing and maintaining good One Health practice.”

Photos

Funding

This CPD was funded from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Internal Events Survey information

The European Commission (EC) requires all dissemination and communication activities, and events to be reported. This information has been reported through the [Internal Events Survey](#) on the OHEJP website, which collects data and is reported to the EC.

Name of the activity:	Continuing Professional Development Module - Rapid Diagnostics and Harmonization of Diagnostic Tests		
Date:	2-4 November, 2022		
Place:	Copenhagen, Denmark		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	45	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Annex 1: "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!
One Health EJP
Continuing Professional Development Module
Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests

Date:
 2nd - 4th November, 2022

Location:
 Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark and online.

Audience:
 Twenty onsite participants, including both microbiologists and epidemiologists, and up to 100 online participants.
 One Health EJP consortium members with interest in the microbiological and epidemiological aspects of laboratory diagnostics.
 PhD Candidates & Early Career Researchers are welcome to apply.

@OneHealthEJP ONE Health EJP
 #OneHealthEJP #OHEJPCpd2022 #StrongerTogether

Annex 2: Full Promotional Flyer

One Health EJP
Continuing Professional Development Module
Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests

Date:
 2nd - 4th November, 2022

Location:
 Statens Serum Institut and DTU Food, Copenhagen, Denmark and online.

Audience:
 Twenty onsite participants, including both microbiologists and epidemiologists, and up to 100 online participants.
 One Health EJP consortium members with interest in the microbiological and epidemiological aspects of laboratory diagnostics.
 PhD Candidates & Early Career Researchers are welcome to apply.

@OneHealthEJP ONE Health EJP
 #OneHealthEJP #OHEJPCpd2022 #StrongerTogether

Introduction to module
 Diagnostic tests are a key part of investigating and managing an outbreak. New diagnostic methods, including rapid diagnostics, are available and efforts have been made to harmonise diagnostic tests across laboratories and across sectors. This module will discuss the role of diagnostics and related challenges from both the microbiological and epidemiological perspectives. Outbreak case studies based on real outbreaks will actively engage both epidemiologists and microbiologists, walking participants through the different roles that each group plays during an outbreak scenario. Epidemiologists will accompany microbiologists in the laboratory to gain a better understanding of various testing procedures (e.g. PCR, serotyping, whole genome sequencing) and microbiologists will join epidemiologists in conducting epidemiological analyses typical during an outbreak investigation. This structure will allow each group to improve their understanding of the perspectives of the other when dealing with an outbreak together, focusing on the effects of applying rapid and/or harmonised diagnostic tests. The module will draw from the experiences and new knowledge from three One Health EJP Joint Integrative Projects: OH-Harmony-CAP, MATRIX, CARE.

This CPD training module is geared towards PhD students and One Health professionals in the early stages of their careers. The training will take place partly in a laboratory setting and partly as a desktop exercise. Participants will need to bring a laptop with them. No additional preparation is required.

Application deadline
 The application deadline is Friday, 23rd September, 2022.

Participation Fees and Accommodation
 There is no participation fee. Accommodation is not included.

Contact
 If you have any questions, please contact: [Caroline Eves](#)

Registration: [here](#)

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Annex 3: Event Programme

One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module: Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests
COPENHAGEN, DENMARK

WEDNESDAY 2nd NOVEMBER 2022

CET SESSION A - hosted by DTU Food, and online

09.00 Welcome and introduction to One Health EJP
Caroline Eves and Rene Hendriksen

09.15 Keynote address
Peter Gerner-Smidt

10.00 **Break**

10.15 One Health surveillance standardisation and harmonisation
Nadia Boisen

10.30 Pathogenic *E. coli*
Flemming Scheutz

11.00 **Break**

11.05 Whole Genomic Sequencing and CGE bioinformatics tools
Jette Sejer Kjelgaard

11.35 Disease surveillance and outbreak investigation
Emily Dibba White

12.00 **Lunch**

SESSION B - hosted by DTU Food

13.00 Introduction to *E. coli* Case Study
Nadia Boisen

13.15 Lab work: Phenotypical and molecular typing and characterisation
Susanne Jespersen, Sarah Morvig Johansson, Nadia Boisen and Rene Hendriksen

14.45 **Break**

15.00 Lab work: Phenotypical and molecular typing and characterisation
Susanne Jespersen, Sarah Morvig Johansson, Nadia Boisen and Rene Hendriksen

18.00 **Social dinner**

THURSDAY 3rd NOVEMBER 2022

CET SESSION C - hosted by DTU Food

09.00 Lab work: Phenotypical and molecular typing and characterisation
Susanne Jespersen, Sarah Morvig Johansson, Nadia Boisen and Rene Hendriksen

10.30 **Break**

10.45 Lab work: Phenotypical and molecular typing and characterisation
Susanne Jespersen, Sarah Morvig Johansson, Nadia Boisen and Rene Hendriksen

12.00 **Lunch**

SESSION D - hosted by DTU Food

13.00 Lab work: Interpretation and visualisation of results
Susanne Jespersen, Sarah Morvig Johansson, Nadia Boisen and Rene Hendriksen

14.30 **Break**

14.45 Epidemiology work: case definition and descriptive epidemiology
Emily Dibba White and Luise Müller

15.45 **Break**

15.55 Epidemiology work: patient interviews and hypothesis generation
Emily Dibba White and Luise Müller

16.30 **End of session**

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One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module: Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests

FRIDAY 4th NOVEMBER 2022

CET SESSION E - hosted by SSI

09.00 Epidemiology work: case control study and results dissemination
Emily Dibba White and Luise Müller

10.15 **Break**

10.30 Upload *E. coli* sequences to CGE
Susanne Jespersen, Nadia Boisen and Rene Hendriksen

11.00 Case study 2
Gojko Bencelovi

12.00 **Lunch**

SESSION F - hosted by SSI, and online

13.00 Retitution based on the experiences from lab and epidemiological analyses
Mia Tarpdahl and Luise Müller

14.00 **Break**

14.15 CPD evaluation
Caroline Eves

14.45 Lessons learned and conclusions
Nadia Boisen, Rene Hendriksen and Caroline Eves

15.30 **Close of workshop**

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